

Report on Data Collection and Enrichment Tools

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1. Introduction

The Data Collection and Enrichment Tool, detailed in Deliverable 5.7, provides a set of methodologies for measuring physical environment features that have been shown to have the greatest impact on human health, both physical and mental. This document is linked to Deliverable 5.7 and contains documentation and links to the public GitHub repository containing the open-source software implementation of the enrichment tools. The primary goal of the data collection methodologies and measurement tools described here was to aid in the enrichment of Equal-Life's cohort data in order to develop consistent exposome indicators for use in the analyses. The generalised methods for measuring various physical environment features and perceived attributes prioritise robustness, consistency, and reproducibility. This in turn facilitates the potential adoption of the tools by researchers and practitioners outside of Equal-Life, who can use customised local data as inputs, configure the parameters, and compare exposure indicators over large and diverse geographical extents. The tools employ the Python programming language and the public GitHub repository includes detailed instructions for running the code. Moreover, we use open data with at least city-wide or, where available, global coverage. In some cases, we have combined global open datasets with more nuanced freely available local official data. This demonstrates that stakeholders outside of Equal-Life who wish to use our tools can also employ customised datasets in order to achieve more accurate and reliable analyses at the local level.

2. Data collection

The input data used to calculate the exposure metrics covered by the enrichment tool are sourced from open sources with at least city-wide or, where available, global coverage. This ensures consistency and comparability across broad and diverse geographical areas. When implementing some of the metrics, we enriched global datasets with more nuanced local open datasets. Researchers and practitioners within or outside Equal-Life who wish to use our tools can customise input data processes by feeding the metrics with detailed local datasets. Table 1 summarises the input data sources used in the calculation of the exposure metrics, and the following paragraphs describe the characteristics of the main data sources.

OpenStreetMap (OSM). OSM is a publicly available crowd-sourced mapping platform that contains spatial data at a high granularity with ever-increasing completeness (Barrington-Leigh & Millard-Ball, 2017). It is a valuable source of urban morphology and land use data and its expanding coverage allows replication across diverse geographical contexts. OSM is updated and coded on a regular basis in accordance with consistent and community-led guidelines (Boeing, 2021). It can be used for deriving street network data, pedestrian and cycling infrastructure, administrative and other areal boundaries, and points of interest (POIs) (e.g., parks, playgrounds, schools, libraries, and other amenities) (Psyllidis et al., 2022). Its well-documented taxonomy¹ also ensures that the physical environment features are defined consistently across the different study areas. The identified features are queried from the OSM database through the Overpass Application Programming Interface (API)² or the OSMnx³ library. Despite their numerous benefits, open-source platforms such as OSM may still suffer from

¹ https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Map_features (accessed 28 February 2023).

² https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Overpass_API (accessed 28 February 2023).

³ <https://github.com/gboeing/osmnx> (accessed 28 February 2023), see also (Boeing, 2017).

coverage and data quality biases, such as varying representation quality across geographic areas or even different parts of the same city (Psyllidis et al., 2022). There are also time-related biases. Because of less user input, OSM data from previous years tend to be less complete. As a result, even if an area is represented differently over time (e.g., in terms of the number of buildings, street layout, or points of interest) this does not always reflect actual changes in the built environment.

Street-level imagery. Street-level imagery is another source with great potential for physical environment exposure analysis. Unlike well-known satellite imagery, this source provides ground-level panoramic views of urban and rural environments. Street-level imagery can be extracted through APIs from both proprietary (e.g., Google Street View) and user-generated public (e.g., Mapillary) online repositories. We rely on street-level imagery to extract experiential and perceptual environmental qualities, which gives a fresh perspective on how we represent the physical environment. Street-level imagery simulates the process of a person walking down the street, providing a three-dimensional overview of visible spatial elements (e.g., building facades, trees, street furniture). Subjective perceptions of the physical environment such as perceived safety and attractiveness are often difficult to quantify across large spatial extents in a robust and comprehensive manner. We strive to develop reliable and, to the greatest extent possible, reproducible crowdsourcing methodologies to enrich street-level imagery with human-generated annotations of environmental perceptions in order to measure city-wide perceptions of physical environment features.

Global Human Settlements Layer (GHSL). GHSL is an open geospatial repository, generated and consistently coded by the European Commission to provide spatially detailed information on populations and settlements worldwide. The datasets are created using a combination of satellite imagery, census data, and volunteered geographic information such as OSM. The data coverage ranges from global datasets (e.g., the GHSL Data Package 2022⁴) to pan-European built-up layers (the European Settlement Map⁵) to analytical data (e.g., the Urban Centre Database⁶). We use GHSL data to consistently distinguish urban from rural areas using the “degree of urbanisation” methodology⁷, defined by specific cut-off values on resident population and built-up surface share in a 1x1 km uniform global grid (Dijkstra et al., 2021; Florczyk et al., 2019).

Local open data sources. Examples of local open data sources used when implementing some of the metrics include detailed land use data from the Dutch Basisregistratie Grootschalige Topografie (BGT), population data from the Dutch Central Bureau for Statistics (CBS), and school addresses from the Dutch Education Executive Agency (DUO), used in capturing street infrastructure, aspects of access on the move, and the co-accessibility index. Researchers and practitioners within or outside Equal-Life can use local input data sources of similar detail to tailor the measurement of indicators in local contexts.

⁴ <https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datasets.php> (accessed 28 February 2023).

⁵ https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/esm_R2019.php (accessed 28 February 2023).

⁶ https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ghs_stat_ucdb2015mt_r2019a.php (accessed 28 February 2023).

⁷ <https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/degurba.php> (accessed 28 February 2023).

Table 1. Input data sources for the calculation of each exposure metric covered by the enrichment tool.

Metric	Source	URL	Comments
Sidewalk space	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OSM street network Local high granularity land use polygons (e.g., Dutch BGT) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.openstreetmap.org/ https://www.kadaster.nl/zakelijk/registraties/basisregistraties/bgt 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BGT is a Dutch local data source and can be replaced with similar data on road segment geometries from other geographical contexts. BGT data was manually downloaded, filtered on road segment data, and stored as a shapefile.
Cycling space	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OSM street network Local high granularity land use polygons (e.g., Dutch BGT) 	https://www.openstreetmap.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BGT is a Dutch local data source and can be replaced with similar data on road segment geometries from other geographical contexts. BGT data was manually downloaded, filtered on road segment data, and stored as a shapefile.
Betweenness centrality	OSM street network	https://www.openstreetmap.org/	
Intersection closeness centrality	OSM street network	https://www.openstreetmap.org/	
Sinuosity	OSM street network	https://www.openstreetmap.org/	
Spatial accessibility	OSM street network, greenspaces, amenities	https://www.openstreetmap.org/	
Co-accessibility	OSM street network Local high granularity population data (e.g., Dutch CBS 100m ² square grid cells)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.openstreetmap.org/ https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/dossier/nederland-regionaal/geografische-data/kaart-van-100-meter-bij-100-meter-met-statistieken 	CBS 100m by 100m grid cells are Dutch local data sources and can be replaced with similar data on populations from other geographical contexts.
Access to greenspace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OSM street network, greenspaces Local high granularity population data (e.g., Dutch CBS 100m grid cells) Local educational facility locations (e.g., Dutch DUO school addresses data) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.openstreetmap.org/ https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/dossier/nederland-regionaal/geografische-data/kaart-van-100-meter-bij-100-meter-met-statistieken https://www.duo.nl/open_onderwijsdata/primair-onderwijs/scholen-en-adressen/schoolvestigingen-basisonderwijs.jsp https://www.duo.nl/open_onderwijsdata/voortgezet-onderwijs/adressen/vestigingen.jsp 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CBS 100m² square grid cells are Dutch local data sources and can be replaced with similar data on populations from other geographical contexts. The DUO school address data is a Dutch local data source and can be replaced with similar data on the locations of educational facilities. In the case of the Dutch DUO data, addresses were converted to geolocations using a geocoding script that is also provided with this deliverable. Ideally, however, one would use a data set that already contains geolocations (i.e., coordinates, instead of address text strings).

Metric	Source	URL	Comments
Access to playgrounds	OSM playgrounds, schoolyards, greenspaces, water bodies, street network, and railway infrastructure	https://www.openstreetmap.org/	
Perceived attributes of the physical environment (safety, attractiveness, perceptions of greenspaces)	OSM street network Street-level imagery Crowdsourcing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● https://www.openstreetmap.org/ ● https://www.cyclomedia.com/en ● https://www.google.com/streetview/ ● https://www.mapillary.com/ ● https://www.prolific.co/ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The street-level imagery data can be obtained from various sources such as Google Street View, Mapillary, or Cyclomedia. ● Crowdsourcing platforms such as Prolific can be used to collect what attributes of the physical environment affect how people perceive different places.

3. Collection of physical environment data

Physical environment data for exposure enrichment were obtained from the sources described in Sect. 2 and summarised in Table 1 using either dedicated APIs or direct downloads, depending on the source. The Overpass API was used to retrieve OSM data, and spatial features such as general amenities, playgrounds, and parks were obtained using tags from the OSM taxonomy of map features. The code repositories described in Sect. 4 include detailed lists of the spatial features used for each query. Street-level imagery was also obtained using dedicated APIs provided by various platforms (e.g., Google Street View, Mapillary, Cyclomedia). GHSL, CBS, BGT, and DUO datasets were obtained directly from the corresponding databases.

3.1 Defining and processing administrative boundaries

The calculation of exposure metrics requires a robust and consistent definition of areal boundaries. In general, we used the Overpass API to obtain the area boundaries of the study regions from OSM. On a few occasions, we extended the administrative boundaries by 2-3 kilometres. This is especially true for topological measures prone to boundary effects, such as street betweenness centrality and intersection closeness centrality (Hillier et al., 1993; Ratti et al., 2004; Psyllidis et al., 2021). When calculated within urban areas, the topological and greenspace accessibility metrics produce more consistent results. We used the GHSL degree of urbanisation methodology in conjunction with the OSM administrative boundaries to create a consistent definition of urban areas.

4. A reproducible software framework for data enrichment

We developed an open-source software framework for calculating the various metrics to facilitate the adoption of our measurement and enrichment tools. Deliverable 5.7 contains detailed descriptions of how each metric was created. The sections that follow describe how to configure the data collection and enrichment set of tools, as well as step-by-step instructions for installing and running the code for each metric. The repositories are open-source, allowing researchers and practitioners to replicate our methodologies and potentially apply them to different geographical regions.

4.1 Setup configuration

All our metrics and the tools to calculate them were developed in [Python 3](#). In addition, some tools make use of the [Jupyter Notebook](#) platform. In each of the following sections, we provide a link to the GitHub repository that contains our code and a “requirements.txt” file that lists the dependencies and required libraries that must be installed for the code to run correctly. Typical steps to use – and possibly customise – our tools are as follows:

1. Fork the repository of your interest.
2. Clone the repository locally.
3. Create a virtual environment in Python (optional but recommended).
4. Install the required packages in this virtual environment using the command “*pip install -r requirements.txt*”.
5. Update data paths to your desired local configuration. If necessary, download and pre-process data, or update data paths to local data sources of your area of interest.
6. Run the code of your interest.

4.2 Tools for measuring physical environment features

4.2.1 Street design features and physical layout

Description: Our Python library calculates the average width of street infrastructure, based on an input dataset of high-granularity street segment polygons (e.g., polygons depicting sidewalks or bike paths).

Installation and usage: To install the library, after the 4th step of the setup configuration, you need to run the following command: `“pip install dist/ctwalk-0.1.0-py3-none-any.whl”`. Then, follow the example provided on the repository’s README page or the Jupyter Notebook with examples provided by the repository.

- The notebook “examples.ipynb” shows how to use *ctwalk* to calculate the average width of each street segment’s sidewalks or bike paths. This example relies on a high-granularity local land use data set, such as the Dutch BGT, which depicts each sidewalk or bike path as a polygon. This can be tailored to other geographical contexts.

Code: <https://github.com/MiliasV/ctwalk>

4.2.2 Street network metrics

Description: Our Python library calculates street betweenness, street intersection centrality, and street sinuosity.

Installation and usage: To install the library, after the 4th step of the setup configuration (Sect. 4.1), you should run the following command: `“pip install dist/ctwalk-0.1.0-py3-none-any.whl”`. Then, follow the example provided on the repository’s README page or the Jupyter Notebook with examples provided by the repository.

- The notebook “examples.ipynb” demonstrates how *ctwalk* can be used to node closeness, edge betweenness, and edge sinuosity to a road network.

Code: <https://github.com/MiliasV/ctwalk>

4.2.3 Access to amenities

Description: Code to estimate pedestrian accessibility to amenities.

Installation and usage: There are four main steps you should follow to estimate accessibility to amenities.

1. Use the “*collect_osm_data.ipynb*” notebook to collect amenities from OpenStreetMap for the city of your interest.
2. Collect or prepare the data that include the locations (e.g., dwellings) for which you want to identify the amenities within an X-minute walk.
3. Use the “*calculate_walkable_isochrones.py*” Python file to estimate the walkable environments for each desired location.

4. Use the “*calculate_place_isochrone_intersection.py*” to identify which amenities are accessible to each of the locations.

Code: <https://github.com/MiliasV/coaccessibility>

4.2.4 Co-accessibility index

Description: Code for calculating the demographics of people who can walk to amenities in 5, 10, and 15 minutes.

Installation and usage: There are four main steps you should follow to estimate the co-accessibility of amenities.

5. Use the “*collect_osm_data.ipynb*” notebook to collect urban amenities from OpenStreetMap for the city of your interest.
6. Collect residential data. If you are interested in a Dutch city you can use the “*get_cbs_data.ipynb*” notebook to collect population data from the Netherlands from CBS (resolution of 100x100m² grid). Otherwise, you should adjust the code of the next steps according to the structure of your population data. The population data you use should include the demographic information you are interested in (e.g., age, income, ethnicity).
7. Using your population data, use the “*calculate_walkable_isochrones.py*” Python file to estimate the 5, 10, and 15-minute walkable environments. Each area in your population data will have a different isochrone.
8. To determine which amenities are accessible to which population groups, use the “*calculate_place_isochrone_intersection.py*”.
9. You can now aggregate this information based on your interests and the data you have for each population group. For example, you can compute the total number of people who have access to each amenity.

Code: <https://github.com/MiliasV/coaccessibility>

4.2.5 Access to greenspaces

Description: Code for calculating greenspace accessibility via pedestrian walksheds and commuting people. On-the-move calculations require a few manual steps to calculate patronage betweenness using the *Urban Network Analysis* toolbox for Rhino (Sevtsuk & Kalvo, 2015; Sevtsuk, 2021), which are specified in further detail in “*additional example-commuting patterns for cohort data.ipynb*”.

Installation and usage: This tool includes several Jupyter Notebooks, including code developed for the journal article on children’s and adolescents’ access to greenspace (Teeuwen et al., 2023) and additional examples.

- Notebooks numbered 1 to 9 are specifically developed for the journal article on children’s and adolescents’ access to greenspace and are written to run in order.
 - **Notebooks 1-6**

- To collect greenspace and pedestrian street network data, and generate pedestrian walksheds, use *“1-greenspaces and network.ipynb”*.
- To collect information on where children and adolescents live, use *“2-residential environments.ipynb”*. This code makes use of CBS population data from the Netherlands (resolution of 100x100m square grid), which includes children, adolescents, and general population numbers. If you want to run this code for different countries, adjust the data and code accordingly.
- To collect information on where children and adolescents go to school, use *“3-educational environments.ipynb”*. This code takes as input the Dutch DUO school locations. It converts addresses into coordinates. If you want to run this code for different countries, adjust the data and code accordingly. Alternatively, you can use OSM school data, which the code also supports.
- Run *“4-on the move preprocessing.ipynb”* to pre-process the collected data thus far in order to run patronage betweenness analysis in Rhino, *manually* perform the patronage betweenness analysis in Rhino, and then run *“5-on the move postprocessing.ipynb”* to post-process its output.
- Run *“6-accessibility.ipynb”* to calculate greenspace accessibility values for children and adolescents from home, school, and commuting settings, as well as a baseline accessibility value.
- **Notebooks 7-8**
 - *“7-quantitative analysis.ipynb”* to perform statistical analyses on the accessibility results across multiple cities (e.g., Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague), as well as to generate tables and visuals.
 - *“8-qualitative analysis.ipynb”* to create visuals for qualitative analysis of accessibility results across multiple cities (e.g., Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague).
- **Notebooks 9 a-b-c:** these alternatives to Notebooks 5, 6, and 7 explore the implications of calculating adolescents’ access when using different settings.
- Three additional Jupyter Notebooks with complementary examples:
 - When you have cohort data that include home and school addresses (e.g., as in the BREATHE cohort study in Barcelona), use *“additional example-commuting patterns for cohort data.ipynb”* to generate a commuting heatmap for the cohort. This Notebook contains instructions on how to perform the manual steps required to calculate patronage betweenness values (see Fig. 10 in Deliverable 5.7).
 - To generate pedestrian walksheds around parks for any urban area of interest worldwide, use *“additional example-osm park pedestrian walksheds.ipynb”*. Published example for Barcelona, Spain (see Fig. 9 in Deliverable 5.7).
 - If you wish to compare the outcomes of various measures for park exposure (availability, accessibility via Euclidean distance buffer zones, and accessibility via network distance buffer zones), run *“additional example-comparing greenspace accessibility methods.ipynb”*. This Notebook calculates the number of people who have access to greenspaces using a Dutch local population dataset. This part can be adapted to other geographical contexts or commented out if such values are not required (see Fig. 5 in Deliverable 5.7).

Code: <https://github.com/rflteeuwen/GreenspaceAccessibility>

4.2.6 Access to playgrounds

Description: Code for calculating child’s play access: young children's access to a variety of play spaces while accounting for potential barriers in the urban environment.

Installation and usage: This tool includes a number of Jupyter Notebooks. These Notebooks were created for the paper on child’s play access (Teeuwen & Psyllidis, 2023) and are written to run in order. The code is written for areas in Utrecht, Milan, and Ljubljana, which were used as case studies in the co-design process of the child’s play accessibility metric. The final child's play accessibility metric is implemented in Notebooks 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4. The rest of the Notebooks were made for the co-design process.

- To collect OSM data on barriers to children, run “3.1 barriers 3 cities.ipynb” and to collect OSM data on play spaces for children, run “3.2 attractions 3 cities.ipynb”.
- To calculate the child’s play accessibility metric based on these barriers and play spaces, run “3.3 independent access 3 cities.ipynb”.
- To visualise and analyse the results of the child’s play accessibility metric, run “3.4 visualization.ipynb”. This notebook visualises accessibility for the three case study areas. It also calculates how many children are estimated to have access to play space in the case study area in Utrecht using the child's play accessibility metric, as opposed to other metrics. This part of the code relies on population data from the Netherlands from CBS (resolution of 100x100m square grid).

Code: <https://github.com/rflteeuwen/ChildsPlayAccessibility>

4.2.7 Perceived attributes of the physical environment

Description: Code for (1) calculating natural surveillance scores and (2) running the crowdsourcing tool for capturing perceived attributes of the physical environment.

Installation and usage: The repository, which includes the code for calculating natural surveillance scores, includes detailed instructions for running the code. The three main steps are as follows:

1. The facade labelling model used to detect building openings in street-level imagery can be downloaded [here](#).
2. Within the Google Cloud platform, obtain an API key for the Google Street View Static API.
3. Run the code.

The repository, which includes the code of the crowdsourcing tool, contains detailed instructions for running the code. The three main steps are as follows:

1. Install all software dependencies as mentioned in the repository.
2. Create the database according to the SQL file that is shared in the repository.

3. Build the tool and run it locally.

Code: Natural Surveillance → <https://github.com/timovanasten/natural-surveillance>

Crowdsourcing Tool → <https://github.com/shahinsharifi/subjectivity>

7. References

- Barrington-Leigh, C. and Millard-Ball, A., 2017. The world's user-generated road map is more than 80% complete. *PLoS one*, 12(8), p.e0180698.
- Boeing, G., 2017. OSMnx: New methods for acquiring, constructing, analyzing, and visualizing complex street networks. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 65, pp.126-139.
- Boeing, G., 2021. Spatial information and the legibility of urban form: Big data in urban morphology. *International Journal of Information Management*, 56, p.102013.
- Dijkstra, L., Florczyk, A.J., Freire, S., Kemper, T., Melchiorri, M., Pesaresi, M. and Schiavina, M., 2021. Applying the degree of urbanisation to the globe: A new harmonised definition reveals a different picture of global urbanisation. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 125, p.103312.
- Florczyk, A.J., Corbane, C., Ehrlich, D., Freire, S., Kemper, T., Maffenini, L., Melchiorri, M., Pesaresi, M., Politis, P., Schiavina, M. and Sabo, F., 2019. GHSL data package 2019. *Luxembourg, EUR*, 29788(10.2760), p.290498.
- Hillier, B., Penn, A., Hanson, J., Grajewski, T. and Xu, J., 1993. Natural movement: or, configuration and attraction in urban pedestrian movement. *Environment and Planning B: planning and design*, 20(1), pp.29-66.
- Psyllidis, A., Duarte, F., Teeuwen, R., Salazar Miranda, A., Benson, T. and Bozzon, A., 2021. Cities and infectious diseases: Assessing the exposure of pedestrians to virus transmission along city streets. *Urban Studies*, p.00420980211042824.
- Psyllidis, A., Gao, S., Hu, Y., Kim, E.K., McKenzie, G., Purves, R., Yuan, M. and Andris, C., 2022. Points of Interest (POI): a commentary on the state of the art, challenges, and prospects for the future. *Computational Urban Science*, 2(1), p.20.
- Ratti, C., 2004. Space syntax: some inconsistencies. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and design*, 31(4), pp.487-499.
- Sevtsuk, A., 2021. Estimating pedestrian flows on street networks: revisiting the betweenness index. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 87(4), pp.512-526.
- Sevtsuk, A. and Kalvo, R., 2015. Urban network analysis toolbox for rhinoceros 3D. *Singapore: City Form Lab*.
- Teeuwen, R., Psyllidis, A. and Bozzon, A., 2023. Measuring children's and adolescents' accessibility to greenspaces from different locations and commuting settings. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 100, p.101912.
- Teeuwen, R. and Psyllidis, A., 2023 (in press). Easy as child's play? Co-designing a network-based metric for children's access to play space. To appear in the *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Computational Urban Planning and Urban Management*, Montreal, Canada.

